

ELASTOPLASTIC FINITE-ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF HEAT-SEALED AREA IN LAMINATED PLASTIC FILM USED FOR LIQUID PACKAGING BAGS UNDER DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: In this study, stress and strain on a cross section of a heat-sealed area in laminated plastic film used for liquid packaging bags under different temperatures were analyzed using the elastoplastic finite-element method upon application of static load to dynamically investigate the cause of bursting of the bags. Prior to the analysis, Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios and stress-strain curves of the components constituting the film, which were necessary in the analysis, were measured using a grid method. In addition, the force acting on an area was determined by measuring the pressure in the bags. The shapes of cross sections obtained by the analysis of their material properties and the force were in good agreement with those obtained by cutting frozen bags under compressive loads. As a result, characteristic distributions of equivalent stress and strain, which depend on temperature, were found in the area.

KEYWORDS: finite element analysis, stress, strain, liquid packaging bag, plastic film, grid method, heat sealing

INTRODUCTION

The use of plastic containers for packing foods is steadily increasing recently. However, since the majority of these containers are not recycled but used in the one-way mode, plastic garbage has become a serious environmental problem. Under such circumstances, the reduction of volume and thickness of these wastes is required to minimize their total quantity. Attracting attention in this respect are flexible packages which not only facilitate reduction of volume and thickness but can also be folded into compact volumes for easy recovery. Particularly advantageous among them are liquid packages made of laminated film in which the quantity of plastic used can be reduced to 1/5-1/10 that used for hard packages.

However, the disadvantage is that, since a thin laminated film is used, it can readily cause possible bursting of packages due to temperature changes or shock during transportation. To overcome this disadvantage, knowledge of the dynamic mechanism of bursting is necessary.

Until now, very little has been known about this mechanism, and there have been only a few experimental studies on bursting[1]-[3].

In this study, stress and strain on a cross section of a heat-sealed area, at which most bursting occurs, in a laminated plastic film used for liquid packaging bags under different temperatures were analyzed using the elastoplastic finite-element method upon application of static load, to dynamically investigate the cause of bursting of the bags. Prior to the analysis, Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios and stress-strain curves of the components constituting the film, which were necessary in the analysis, were measured in tension tests using a grid method. In addition, the force acting on an area was determined by measuring the pressure in the bags. The shape of the cross section obtained by the analysis of their material properties and force was compared with that obtained by cutting frozen bags under compressive loads. The analytical results for equivalent stress and strain are discussed.

LIQUID PACKAGING BAG

Structure of Laminated Film

Figure 1 shows the liquid packaging bags used in this study, which were made of laminated film and contained about 17ml of water. Three sides of these bags were heat-sealed by an automatic packaging machine (NT-Dangan, Nippon Seiki) under the same sealing conditions, which were determined based on the plastic film test (JIS-Z-1707-1975, Japanese Standards Association) for food packages.

Fig. 1: Shape and dimensions of liquid

The laminated film consisted of nylon, NY, (15 μ m in thickness), polyethylene, PE, (25 μ m in thickness) and ethylene vinylacetate copolymer, EVA, (25 μ m in thickness) used in common, as shown in Fig.2. Two films, PE and EVA, were combined into one film, called a seal layer, PE-EVA, during heat sealing.

Shape of Cross Section of Heat-Sealed Area

Fig. 2: Cross section of laminated plastic film used for liquid packaging bag.

Liquid packaging bags were frozen at a temperature of -20°C in a thermostatic oven in order to investigate the shape of the cross section of the heat-sealed area of the bags under compressive loads, F , between 0 and 1kN, as shown in Fig.3. The frozen bags were cut in the longitudinal direction, as shown in Fig.3. The cross sections were observed using a microscope before thawing.

Figure 4 shows two examples of the sections observed at loads, F , of 0N and 400N. Figure 4(a) was used to model a cross section of the heat-sealed area of the bags for the finite-element analysis.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED FILM

Young's moduli, E , Poisson's ratios, ν , and stress-strain curves of NY and PE-EVA, which were necessary in the finite-element analysis, were measured in tension tests using a grid method. Generally, laminated plastic film used for liquid packaging bags is made by together rolling NY film, which is formed beforehand, and PE and EVA films, which are formed from powder materials by heating and extraction in the manufacturing process of the laminated film. NY, PE and EVA films are difficult to completely separate from the laminated film. In this study, NY and PE-EVA films were separated from the laminated film by using ethyl acetate solution immediately after the manufacture of the laminated film.

Figure 5 shows the shape and dimensions of the specimens, which were based on JIS-K-6734, used for obtaining E , ν and stress-strain curves of NY and PE-EVA. Cross grids with 2mm

pitch were printed on the surface of the specimens using a simple printing technique, as shown in Fig.6. The specimens were set in an electric furnace equipped with a universal test machine (RTM-1T, Orientech) with 10kN capacity, as shown in Fig.7, and subjected to tensile loads at a rate of 5mm/min at temperatures of -10, 0, 20 and 40°C.

Fig. 3: Compression of liquid packaging bag used to investigate cross section shape of heat-sealed area.

Fig. 4: Cross section of heat-sealed area cut from bags frozen under compression load, F .

Fig.5: Specimen for measuring material properties

Fig. 6: Grid printed on specimen surface.

The images of the specimen surfaces with the grids were recorded using an 8mm video camera via a CCD camera, in tension tests, as shown in Fig.7. The amounts of tensile loads at which the images were recorded were read off from a load counter photographed using another 8mm video camera.

The stress, σ , was obtained by dividing axial load by the initial cross-sectional area of the film specimen. The longitudinal and lateral strains, ϵ_L and ϵ_T , which were measured in the directions parallel and normal to tensile load, were obtained by measuring the deformations, δ_L and δ_T , in the original lengths, δ_L and δ_T , between two line segments, which were selected from the line segments forming grids drawn on the specimen surface, and dividing δ_L and δ_T by D_L and D_T , respectively.

In order to measure δ_L and δ_T , images output by a video printer were used. δ_L and δ_T in the range of elasticity were difficult to accurately measure because they were small. Hence, images enlarged 400 times by a digital duplicating machine were used.

Young's modulus, E , is defined as the ratio of σ to ϵ_L . Poisson's ratio, ν , was obtained from the ratio of ϵ_T to ϵ_L . Young's moduli, E , and Poisson's ratios, ν , obtained are given in Table 1. Figure 8 shows the stress-strain curves. Young's moduli of all films decreased and Poisson's ratios increased as temperature increased.

Fig. 7: Setup for measuring material properties

Table 1: Mechanical properties of NY and PE-EVA

Young's modulus, E (GPa)				
Component	-10°C	0°C	20°C	40°C
NY	6.75	4.00	4.06	1.92
PE-EVA	0.122	0.115	0.092	0.044
Poisson's ratio, ν				
Component	-10°C	0°C	20°C	40°C
NY	0.21	0.36	0.39	0.39
PE-EVA	0.21	0.34	0.36	0.42

(a) NY

(b) PE-EVA

Fig.8: Stress-strain curves

FORCE ACTING ON HEAT-SEALED AREA

The force acting on a heat-sealed area of liquid package bags, which is necessary in the finite-element analysis, was estimated from pressure, p , measured in the bags under static compression, F , in the manner similar to that shown in Fig.3. The internal pressure was measured using a pressure gage (PS-2KA, Kyowa). The gage was wrapped in polyethylene film to keep out the moisture contained in liquid packaging bags and was inserted into bags from a heat-sealed area which was partly opened. Then, the opened area was heat-sealed, using a simple heat-sealing equipment, to prevent the leakage of water.

The electrical signal, voltage, obtained from the gage was measured using a digital oscilloscope via a dynamic strain meter. The pressure was determined from the voltage using the relationship between the voltage obtained from the same gage under a given pressure in a pressure container with a pressure regulator and the pressure.

Consequently, the internal pressure, p , was proportional to the external load, F , as expressed by

$$p = F/A , \tag{1}$$

where A is the area in which the load acts, as shown in Fig.3. In this study, an area of $A=2709\text{mm}^2$ was used, which was obtained experimentally.

Figure 9 shows an example of the relationships among F , p and tension, T , acting on a cross section of film, which is encountered over a wide range of p , except in the initial stage at

which p is low. From this figure, T was found to be proportional to p . Hence, T is expressed by

$$T = rbp, \quad (2)$$

where r is the radius of parts not subjected to F and b is the depth of the bag.

In this study, $r=3.5\text{mm}$, which was determined in experiments described in the above section, and $b=10\text{mm}$ were used. Hence, the relationship between T and p used in the finite-element analysis was expressed by $T(\text{N})=35p(\text{MPa})$.

The mean bursting load for 20 bags was about 1kN.

Fig. 9: Force acting on heat-sealed area

STRESS AND STRAIN IN HEAT-SEALED AREA

To analyze stress and strain in the heat-sealed area under static load, the elastoplastic finite-element method was used. MARC was used as the analytical software.

The models of packaging bags used for this analysis were approximately Y-shaped under the no-load condition, as shown in Fig.10. The shape of the models was determined with reference to cross sections of heat-sealed areas of the bags under the no-load condition, as shown in Fig.4(a). Only the upper half was used because the models showed symmetry between the upper and lower halves. At the midpoint between points C and D , only the displacement in the x direction, u , was fixed, and between points A and B , only the displacement in the y direction, v , was fixed. In order to keep line segment $C-D$ at the load points straight, a material with Young's modulus of 400GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3 was used for elements in the neighborhood of line $C-D$. Figure 11 shows a typical mesh in which plane strain elements were used.

Incremental loading was used for this analysis. In this analysis, an incremental load, ΔT , of 0.09N ($\Delta\sigma_{ap}=0.14\text{MPa}$) was applied from $T_{min}=0\text{N}$ to $T_{max}=18\text{N}$, which was determined from

Eqns 1 and 2 with reference to the mean burst load, as described in the above section. From Eqn 2, the incremental pressure, Δp , was given as $\Delta p(\text{MPa}) = \Delta T/rb = \Delta T(\text{N})/35$.

Failure, which was defined as when the maximum stress or strain in the model became equal to that at the fracture point on the strain-stress curve of NY or PE-EVA, at temperatures of -10, 0, 20 and 40°C occurred at $\sigma_{ap} = 20.6, 15.5, 12.2$ and 7.0 MPa. The strength of the bags under static load decreased as the temperature increased. The strength at 40°C was about one-third and half of those at -10°C and 20°C, respectively.

Figure 12 shows the equivalent stresses, σ_{eq} , at temperatures of -10, 0, 20 and 40°C under an applied load, σ_{ap} , of 7.0MPa. In this figure, σ_{eq} is shown on models deformed by σ_{ap} . The black regions were assigned values below $\sigma_{eq} = 7\text{MPa}$ and the white ones, above $\sigma_{eq} = 7\text{MPa}$. The color of the regions changes from black to white as the value of σ_{eq} increases from 7MPa to 70MPa.

The larger stresses were obtained at the concave part in NY and at point B, shown in Fig.10, in PE-EVA. This indicates that most of the applied load was transmitted from NY to PE-EVA near point B. The stress at point B, which was considered as the most important one from the fact that the failure occurred near this point in experiments[2], decreased as the temperature increased.

Figures 13, 14 and 15 show the equivalent strains, ϵ_{eq} , under applied loads, σ_{ap} , at temperatures of -10, 20 and 40°C, respectively. Figure 16 shows ϵ_{eq} at temperatures of -10, 0, 20 and 40°C under $\sigma_{ap} = 7.0\text{MPa}$. In these figures, ϵ_{eq} is shown on models deformed by ϵ_{ap} . The black regions are assigned values below $\epsilon_{eq} = 0.1$ and the white ones, above $\epsilon_{eq} = 0.1$, in which the plastic zones in NY and PE-EVA were obtained.

Fig.10: Model used for finite-element analysis

Fig.11: Typical mesh: 528 nodes, 584 elements

Fig.12: Effects of temperature on equivalent stress under $\sigma_{ap} = 7.0\text{MPa}$

Fig.13: Effects of applied load, σ_{ap} , on equivalent strain at -10°C

The deformation at -10°C under $\sigma_{ap}=5.5\text{MPa}$ which corresponds to about $F=280\text{N}$ is similar to that obtained experimentally and shown in Fig.4(a). The maximum equivalent strain, $\epsilon_{eq(max)}$, at each temperature occurred at point B and increased as the applied load increased. The plastic zones, in which high equivalent strains of over 0.1 exist, spread from point B toward load points in the seal layer as the applied load increased. The increase of temperature caused the increase of $\epsilon_{eq(max)}$ at point B and of the area of the plastic zone.

The above results showed that bursting of bags occurred more easily as the temperature increased. Furthermore, the fracture mode of tension rather than tearing was inferred.

(a) $\sigma_{ap}=2.5\text{MPa}$

(a) $\sigma_{ap}=1.7\text{MPa}$

(b) $\sigma_{ap}=5.5\text{MPa}$

(b) $\sigma_{ap}=3.7\text{MPa}$

(c) $\sigma_{ap}=12.2\text{MPa}$

(c) $\sigma_{ap}=7.0\text{MPa}$

Fig.14: Effects of applied load, σ_{ap} , on equivalent strain at 20°C

Fig.15: Effects of applied load, σ_{ap} , on equivalent strain at 40°C

CONCLUSIONS

Stress and strain on a cross section of a heat-sealed area in laminated plastic film used for liquid packaging bags under different temperatures were analyzed using the elastoplastic finite-element method for the force acting on the area and material properties of the components constituting the film, which were obtained experimentally. The results indicated the following.

- (1) Most of the applied load was transmitted from NY to PE-EVA near the internal boundary point of the heat-sealed cross section.
- (2) The maximum equivalent strain occurred at the internal boundary point, and increased as the applied load increased.
- (3) The increase of temperature caused the increase of the maximum equivalent strain at the internal boundary point.

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